

ISOLATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF FUNGI ASSOCIATED WITH RICE AND MAIZE SPOILAGE IN MUBI NORTH, ADAMAWA STATE

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Abstract

Cereal crops, such as rice and maize, are vulnerable to fungal spoilage even at low moisture content at various stages of processing and storage along the food chain from cultivation, harvesting, handling, marketing, and storage. Fungi are responsible for about 30-70 % quality deterioration in grains obtained directly from farms to open markets, especially when the grains are exposed to dust, poor handling, and unhygienic practices. This study assesses the quality of grains stored in Mubi North Local Government Area Adamawa State, where the samples were purchased and packaged in a polythene bags. The samples were analysed for morphological and microscopic identification of the fungi isolates. The raw data were analysed for the mean frequency distribution table. The results obtained from the market showed that 8 (36.3%) *aspergillus flavus* were present in both the maize and rice samples, 1 (4.5%) *aspergillus niger*, 7 (31.8%) *aspergillus fumigatus*, 1 (4.5%) *rhizopus stolonifer*, and 5 (22.7%) *penicillium natatum*, without the growth of *aspergillus oryzae*. A total of 9 fungi were isolated and identified in the maize samples, and 13 were identified in the rice samples, with a total of 22 (100 %). The results of the samples obtained from the farm showed that 2 fungi were isolated in maize and 10 which are *rhizopus stolonifer*. In rice, *Aspergillus niger*, *aspergillus flavus*, and *aspergillus oryzae* were isolated and identified. The total incidence of fungal isolates identified in the market and farm shows all the fungi and their distribution, respectively. In conclusion, the market grains sample showed a higher frequency of fungal isolates (22) than the farm samples (12). This suggests that grains may become more contaminated during storage, transportation, and marketing or may be attributed to prolonged storage, handling, poor ventilation, and exposure to environmental contaminants.

Introduction

Fungi are a group of diverse eukaryotic organisms that play a symbiotic role in both plants and animals, occurring naturally in air, water, and soil. Fungi are generally associated with cereal grain spoilage (Karfi *et al.*, 2025). Most of these fungi, including *Aspergillus* spp., *Penicillium* spp., *Rhizopus* spp., and *Mucor*, are capable of producing mycotoxins that pose a significant health risk to humans and cause spoilage. These fungi thrive well under warm, temperate, and humid conditions to colonize grains and reduce their quality (Sultan *et al.*, 2022).

Fungi are frequent plant pathogens that cause significant food and feed spoilage (Patricia *et al.*, 2025). Like other cereals, rice is vulnerable to mycotoxins in the fields and during storage (Karfi *et al.*, 2025). An appropriate culture medium serves as a good substrate for fungal growth and toxinogenesis, allowing testing of the toxigenic potential of isolated strains (Azuka *et al.*, 2019; Abdulrazak *et al.*, 2022).

Cereal products represent an important nutrient source for mankind worldwide and are the major source of calories and proteins in Nigeria. Cereal grains constitute an important group of substrates for fermented foods in different parts of Africa, including maize, rice, and sorghum (Hudu *et al.*, 2024). Cereal grains are naturally contaminated with fungi in the field during drying, processing, transportation, and storage, leading to the formation of mycotoxins. A warm temperature, high humidity, and poor storage practices contribute to rapid fungal proliferation. Toxigenic fungi such as *Aspergillus*, *Rhizopus*, and *Penicillium* species are major contaminants of cereal grains, causing significant reductions in crop yield, quality, and safety due to their ability to produce *mycotoxins* (Aasa *et al.*, 2023; Hudu *et al.*, 2024).

Cereal grains, such as maize and rice, are vulnerable to fungal infection at various points along the food chain, including cultivation, harvesting, handling, and marketing. Several authors have reported that fungi can cause between 30 and 70 % quality deterioration in grains obtained directly from farms and open markets, especially when the grains are exposed to dust, moisture, and poor hygienic handling practices (Ode *et al.*, 2021; Deligeorgakis *et al.*, 2023).

Several fungi are commonly associated with spoilage of maize and rice along the agricultural and marketing chain (Aboloma *et al.*, 2016). Members of the genus *Aspergillus* remain the most frequently isolated contaminants, particularly in warm tropical environments. Species such as *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus niger* are widely recognized for producing aflatoxins and ochratoxins, which are potent mycotoxins that pose significant health risks when grains are consumed without adequate quality control (Bennette *et al.*, 2003). *Penicillium chrysogenum* and related spp. are also often detected in grains exposed to moisture or unhygienic handling during harvesting and marketing, contributing to discoloration and nutrient loss. In addition, fast-growing fungi, such as *Rhizopus stolonifer* and *Mucor* spp., are commonly associated with soft rot, texture degradation, and rapid spoilage of grains sold in open markets, where humidity and sanitation levels are difficult to regulate (Salihu *et al.*, 2024).

This study used molecular methods to isolate and identify the presence of fungi associated with spoilage of maize and rice in two different sources from the farm and market in Mubi local government, to improve food safety awareness and guide farmers, traders, and consumers on safe handling and storage practice (Ikechi-Nwogu *et al.*, 2020).

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was conducted in the Mubi North Local Government of Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Sample Collection

Maize and rice samples were collected from two major markets (Kasuwan dole and Sabon Tasha) and two different farms in Adamawa state's Mubi local government area. All samples were collected in a sterile zip lock bag and transported to the laboratory for analysis.

Sample Preparation

The grains samples were sterilized using a 1% solution of aqueous sodium hypochlorite for 1-2 minutes and it was rinsed with sterile distilled water. The grains were blot dried using sterile filter paper, and the grain samples were aseptically ground using a sterile mortar and pestle to obtain homogenate.

Serial Dilution

Serial dilutions were prepared from homogenized samples. One gram (1 g) of ground grain was suspended in 9 ml of sterile distilled water to prepare a 10^{-1} dilution. Aliquots (0.1 ml) from each dilution were plated on PDA plates and incubated at 28 °C for 7 days (Patricia *et al.*, 2025).

Microscopic identification of fungal species

Fungal isolates were identified based on colony morphology, such as color, texture, growth pattern, and pigmentation (Karfi *et al.*, 2022). Microscopic characteristics were determined using lactophenol cotton blue stain. Microscopic structures such as conidiophores, sporangia, hyphae, filaments, and vesicles were examined under 10, 40, and 100 objective lenses (Olugbenga and Chongs, 2024).

Preparation of pure culture

Distinct fungal colonies were selected after incubation and transferred onto fresh PDA to obtain pure isolates. All plates were incubated for an additional 5 days until pure culture was obtained. The pure culture was stored on PDA slants for isolation and characterization (Karfi *et al.*, 2022).

Data Analysis

The raw data were analyzed using a frequency distribution table for the number of isolates, frequency, and percentage of identified fungi.

Result

Table 1 shows the results of fungi isolates in maize and rice samples obtained from the market, where 22 (100%) fungi were recorded from the market sample, with 9 isolates in maize and 13 in rice samples. *A. flavus* was the most predominant isolated fungi in the market rice and maize samples with a total of 8 (36.3 %) isolates, followed by *A. fumigatus* with 7 (31.8 %) isolates, *penicillium* with 5 (22.7 %) isolates, and *A. niger* and *Rhizopus* with 1 (4.5%) isolate in each sample. *A. oryzae* was not detected in the maize and rice samples obtained in markets.

Table 1: Frequency of fungal isolates identified in maize and rice samples obtained from the market

Fungal isolate	Maize	Rice	Total Frequency	Percentage Incidence
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	4	4	8	36.3
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	1	ND	1	4.5
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	3	4	7	31.8
<i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i>	ND	1	1	4.5
<i>Penicillium natatum</i>	1	4	5	22.7
<i>Aspergillus oryzae</i>	ND	ND	0	0
Total	9	13	22	100

Table 2 shows the results of fungi isolated and identified in rice and maize samples obtained in farms after harvest, which indicates that there was a prevalent growth of fungi such as *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Rhizopus*, and *Penicillium* spp. with a total number frequency of 12 (100 %) isolates. The results indicate that there was no prevalence of *Aspergillus flavus*, *A. niger*, *A. fumigatus*, *A. oryzae*, and *Penicillium* spp. detected in the farm samples, except for *Rhizopus* spp., with 2 (16.6 %) isolates in maize and 4 species of *A. flavus*, 2 species of *A. niger*, and 4 species of *A. oryzae* were isolated and identified in rice samples from the farm sample, implying that rice is more susceptible to fungi when not properly dried to a moisture content level of or <14 %. In the maize sample, only *Rhizopus* was detected, whereas the rice sample showed greater diversity with *A. flavus* and *A. oryzae* as the most predominate with 4 isolates each (33.3 %). *A. niger* and *Rhizopus* were detected with two isolates each (16.6 %). *A. fumigatus* and *Penicillium* were not detected in the farm samples.

Table 2: Frequency of fungal isolates identified in maize and rice samples obtained from the sources

Fungal isolate	Maize	Rice	Total Frequency	Percentage incidence (%)
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	ND	4	4	33.3
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	ND	2	2	16.6
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	ND	ND	0	0
<i>Rhizopus</i>	2	ND	2	16.6
<i>Penicillium</i>	ND	ND	0	0
<i>Aspergillus oryzae</i>	ND	4	4	33.3
Total	2	10	12	100

Table 3 presents the results of the total incidence of fungal isolates from the analyzed samples from markets and farms. A total of 34 (100 %) fungal isolates were detected and identified, whereas 22 (35.3 %) *A. flavus* was isolated and identified in grains (rice and maize) samples obtained in the markets and 12 (35. Isolates from the farms. *A. flavus* is the most prevalent fungi from the two sample sources. *Penicillium* is also common in both farm and the market with 5 (14.7%) isolates of *penicillium* in maize but not in rice samples. *Aspergillus* and *Rhizopus* were isolated and identified with 1 isolate in market and 2 isolate in market and farm samples, each with a total of 3(8.8 %) of incidence. Similarly, *A. fumigatus* was isolated and identified with 7 isolates in the market sample and without their incidence in farm samples for both maize and rice, and *penicillium*, and *A. oryzae*, respectively.

Table 3: Total incidence of fungal isolates identified in samples obtained from markets and farms.

Fungal isolate	Markets (maize and rice)	Farm (maize and rice)	Total Frequency	% Incidence
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	8	4	12	35.3
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	1	2	3	8.8
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	7	0	7	20.5
<i>Rhizopus</i>	1	2	3	8.8
<i>Penicillium</i>	5	0	5	14.7
<i>Aspergillus oryzae</i>	0	4	4	11.7
Total	22	12	34	100

Table 4 shows the results of fungal distribution in maize and rice grains in farms and markets, where all the samples showed a minimal level of incidence, except for *A. oryzae*, which was only observed in rice samples with a frequency of 4 (11.7 %). *Aspergillus flavus* had a total incidence of 12 (35.3%), with 4 in maize and 8 in rice, 3 (8.8 %) *aspergillus niger*, with 1 in maize and 2 in rice *rhizopus* species with a total incidence of 3 (8.8 %), and *penicillium* with 1 incidence in maize and 4 in rice with a total incidence of 5 (14.7%).

Table 4: Distribution of fungal isolates

Fungal isolate	Maize	Rice	Total Frequency	% Incidence
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	4	8	12	35.3
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	1	2	3	8.8
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	3	4	7	20.5
<i>Rhizopus</i>	2	1	3	8.8
<i>Penicillium</i>	1	4	5	14.7
<i>Aspergillus oryzae</i>	0	4	4	11.7
Total	11	23	34	100

Discussion

The fungal species associated with spoilage of maize and rice in the Mubi north local government area of Adamawa state were assessed and isolated, characterized, and identified from two different sources: the market and the farm (Okadony *et al.*, 2021). The results showed that rice market samples had the highest prevalence of fungal growth compared with farm samples, which is in agreement with similar findings conducted by other researchers in Nigeria. The results show three fungi belonging to the genera *Aspergillus*, *penicillium*, and *Rhizopus*. *A. flavus* was the most predominant species (35.3%), while other species identified included *A. fumigatus* (20.5%), *Penicillium Spp* (14.7%), *A. oryzae*, *A. niger*, and *Rhizopus spp*. The presence of *Aspergillus* in rice samples could pose a health risk if they are not cooked properly (Aboloma *et al.*, 2016).

The isolation of *Rhizopus spp*, *Penicillium spp*, and *Aspergillus spp* in this study agrees with the work of Onyeze *et al.* (2013) in their study on "isolation and characterization of fungi associated with the spoilage of corn (*Zea mays*) in Enugu." Also the presence of these fungi (Tables 1 and 2) is in line with the work reported by Amadi and Adeniyi (2009) who isolated *Rhizopus spp*, *Penicillium spp*, *Fusarium spp*, and *Aspergillus spp*. in their study. However, the frequency of visible occurrence recorded in this study is in line with the works of many authorities. The percentage of *Aspergillus spp* recorded in this study (Table 3) is greater than that observed by Onyeze *et al.* (2013), who reported the percentage of *Aspergillus spp*.

Fungal contamination was observed in a large proportion of the sample analyzed, indicating that spoilage fungi are common in both rice and maize under prevailing environmental and storage conditions (Ihedioha *et al.*, 2021). The occurrence of fungi in both grains (Table 3) indicates factors such as field infection, harvesting method, drying efficiency, storage conditions, and market handling practices that provide conditions for fungal colonization and proliferation (Sultan *et al.*, 2022).

The predominance of *Aspergillus species* observed in this study agrees with previous findings that *Aspergillus* is one of the most common fungal contaminants of stored cereals in tropical regions. Studies conducted in different

parts of Nigeria have documented similar reports of high *Aspergillus* species occurrence in maize and rice (Karrfi *et al.*, 2025). *Aspergillus* was identified as a dominant contaminant in grains collected from market and storage facilities (El-hassan *et al.*, 2022). A study conducted in Kogi state identified *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* as the most common genera associated with stored maize, with *Fusarium* and *Rhizopus* as the less frequent occurring species (Abdulrazak *et al.*, 2022).

Sultan (2022) reported that several species of *Aspergillus* were identified in this study, including *A. fumigatus*, *A. flavus*, and *A. oryzae*. These fungi are well adapted to warm tropical conditions and grow over a wide temperature range, particularly where grains are inadequately dried and stored under humid conditions. *A. flavus* is known to produce aflatoxin, which is a potent carcinogen associated with liver damage and immune suppression. The dominance of *A. flavus* in these studies is of concern because of its ability to produce aflatoxin, which is the most potent naturally occurring toxins affecting food safety (Aasa *et al.*, 2023).

We also isolated *Penicillium* and *Rhizopus* from maize and rice samples. Other researchers have reported these genera as part of the typical myco-flora of stored cereals (Ojo *et al.*, 2019). *Penicillium* is mostly associated with grain deterioration under suboptimal storage conditions, whereas *Rhizopus* is often observed on damaged kernels and in humid environments.

Both maize and rice samples in this study were contaminated by similar fungal genera (Karrfi *et al.*, 2025). Although slight variation in the frequency of the fungal species was observed, the presence of multiple fungal contamination in both samples indicates a complex fungal community that can cause spoilage in both samples due to enzymatic activities by the fungi, which degrade grain components, leading to deterioration in quality and nutritional value (Ode *et al.*, 2024). Rice was more heavily contaminated than maize, which is consistent with the findings of Deligeorgakis *et al.* (2023), who reported that fungal contamination varies among cereal types depending on grain structure, moisture, water retention, and storage conditions.

The market sample showed a higher frequency of fungal isolates (22) than the farm sample (12), suggesting that grains may become more contaminated during storage, transportation, and marketing or may be attributed to prolonged storage, handling, poor ventilation, and exposure to environmental contaminants. *A. fumigatus* and *Penicillium* were isolated only from farm samples and were absent in market samples, indicating that the species may have been introduced during storage or postharvest. *Rhizopus* spp. were mostly isolated from market samples rather than from farm samples, which may be due to the preference of *Rhizopus* for moist conditions. According to Olugbenga *et al.* (2024), *Rhizopus* spp. are fast-growing fungi that dominate the stage of spoilage but reduce drastically under dry conditions due to competition from other fungi (Akanni and Daeniya, 2020).

Conclusion

In conclusion, when not properly dried, handled, or stored, maize and rice from farms and markets may be infected by a myriad of fungi that produce dangerous mycotoxins that pose health risks to consumers. There is a need for caution in the postharvest handling, storage, transportation, and use of this important food stuff as its contamination with these organisms implies a health risk among consumers when not properly processed. This position concurs with the views of Onyeze *et al.* (2013), who noted that all the fungal organisms identified, isolated, and characterized in their study are capable of causing death to humans and animals resulting from mycotoxins, which could promote fungal growth due to insufficient drying and precarious storage conditions due to low moisture content. Because rice and other agricultural goods play a vital role in human nutrition, the appropriate handling of the output from harvest to consumption is required. Farmers who harvest rice into bags for transportation, marketers, and consumers should all take care to avoid contamination and endeavor to establish an environment that discourages the growth or multiplication of microorganisms.

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